

Prevalence and Patterns of Thyroid Dysfunction among Patients with Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract:

Introduction: Diabetes mellitus (DM) and thyroid dysfunction (TD) are two prevalent endocrine disorders, often coexisting due to their interconnected role in metabolism. In India, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) has become an epidemic, influenced by lifestyle changes. Thyroid disorders, particularly hypothyroidism, are common among T2DM patients, impacting their overall metabolic control. This study aims to assess the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in T2DM patients to improve diagnosis and management strategies.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted over six months at a tertiary care hospital, enrolling 60 adult T2DM patients. Participants with known thyroid disorders or other confounding conditions were excluded. Data collection involved clinical history, anthropometric measurements, and biochemical assessments, including blood glucose, HbA1c, and thyroid profile (TSH, FT3, and FT4). Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS, with p-values <0.05 considered significant.

Results: The study found a significantly higher prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in the diabetic (DM) group (36.7%) compared to the control group (16.7%) (p=0.004). Elevated T3 levels were observed only in the DM group (3.3%, p=0.032), while both high (3.3%) and low (16.7%) T4 levels were significantly more common in the DM group (p=0.036). Additionally, 30% of DM participants had elevated TSH levels, compared to 16.7% in the control group (p=0.021). Subclinical hypothyroidism was present in both groups, though slightly higher in the DM group (16.7%). The DM group also exhibited significantly higher mean fasting blood sugar (149.63 mg/dL vs. 89.73 mg/dL, p<0.001), HbA1c (7.17% vs. 5.07%, p<0.001), and systolic blood pressure (132.60 mmHg vs. 118.67 mmHg, p<0.001) compared to controls, indicating poorer metabolic and cardiovascular profiles among diabetic patients.

Conclusion: Our study shows a notable link between diabetes and thyroid dysfunction, emphasizing the need for regular thyroid screening in diabetic patients for early management.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Thyroid Dysfunction, Hypothyroidism, Metabolic Control.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a collection of common metabolic disorder mainly considered by hyperglycaemia which results commencing from defective insulin secretion or insulin action or together. [1] In India, Type 2 Diabetes mellitus is an epidemic disorder due to social influence and changes in life style. As per WHO estimation, the universal prevalence of Diabetes mellitus was 170 million (2.8%) in 2002, this number expected to grow up to 366 million (4.4%) or more in 2030. [2,3]

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) and thyroid dysfunction (TD) are the two most common endocrine disorders in clinical practice. [4] Excess or deficiency of either insulin or thyroid hormones can result in functional abnormalities of one another, as both of

them are closely involved in cellular metabolism. The association between DM and TD is widely known, with the first studies published in 1979. [5] These differences can be explained by different diagnostic criteria of TD, the degree of iodine intake among different regions, different sensitivities of the TSH assays and the large population diversity. [6] The relationship between TD and DM is characterized by a complex interaction of interdependence. Screening of TD, especially the subclinical dysfunction, in patients with DM is justified because most patients can be asymptomatic.

The prevalence of hypothyroidism was documented in ~4%–5% of population in the developed world, while in Indian population it was reported in

around one in ten adults. [7,8] Various studies have shown a high prevalence of thyroid disorders (TDs) in patients with T2DM (12%–23%). [5,9] Uncontrolled T2DM affects plasma triiodothyronine (T3) as well as thyroxine (T4) levels. [10] The possible reasons postulated for an association between diabetes mellitus and hypothyroidism could be genetic, biochemical, or of hormonal origin. [11] The coexistence of hypothyroidism and type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) may be due to similar autoimmune pathogenesis. Several reports have also indicated a higher prevalence of TD in T2DM patients, with hypothyroidism being the most common disorder. [12] This study was conducted to determine the prevalence of hypothyroidism and the management strategies, including prescription of thyroxine, in Indian patients with T2DM.

Material and Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted to assess the prevalence of thyroid dysfunction (TD) in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM). The study was carried out in a tertiary care hospital over a period of 6 months, with ethical approval obtained from the institutional ethics committee. Written informed consent was collected from all participants before enrollment.

The study included adult patients aged 18 years and above diagnosed with T2DM. Participants were selected from outpatient departments (OPD) and in-patient wards. Patients with pre-existing thyroid disorders, chronic kidney disease, or those on medications affecting thyroid function (such as amiodarone or lithium) were excluded. Pregnant women and critically ill patients were also excluded to minimize confounding factors that could affect thyroid hormone levels.

A sample size of 60 was determined based on the prevalence rates of thyroid dysfunction in T2DM populations reported in previous studies, using a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error. The participants were recruited using a systematic random sampling technique to ensure unbiased data collection.

Clinical history, demographic data, and relevant medical history, including the duration of T2DM were recorded using a structured questionnaire. Anthropometric measurements such as body mass

index (BMI), blood pressure, and waist circumference were measured following standard protocols. Blood samples were collected from all participants after an overnight fast for the assessment of fasting blood glucose, glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), and thyroid profile, including serum thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), free thyroxine (FT4), and free triiodothyronine (FT3) levels.

Thyroid function tests (TFT) were performed using chemiluminescent immunoassays (CLIA). TSH values above 4.2 mIU/L were considered suggestive of hypothyroidism, while subclinical hypothyroidism was defined as elevated TSH with normal FT4 levels. Hyperthyroidism was identified when TSH levels were below 0.4 mIU/L with elevated FT3 or FT4. Blood glucose levels and HbA1c were measured and hypertension was diagnosed based on the American College of Cardiology (ACC) guidelines, with systolic blood pressure ≥ 130 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 80 mmHg.

Data were analyzed using SPSS software version 21.1. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), and categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used to compare categorical variables, and independent t-tests were applied to compare continuous variables between groups. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study data reveals several key demographic characteristics. Age-wise, the majority of participants fall within the 41-50 age group (41.7%), with the control group contributing the most (53.3%). Both the 31-40 and 51-60 age groups show similar representation between the control and diabetic (DM) groups, while the 61-70 and 71-80 age groups account for smaller proportions. The age distribution difference between the two groups is not statistically significant ($p=0.290$). In terms of sex, males constitute the majority in both the control group (70.0%) and the overall sample (61.7%), though females are more prevalent in the DM group (46.7%). However, the difference in sex distribution is also not statistically significant ($p=0.184$).

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age Group	Control (Count, %)	DM (Count, %)
31-40	6 (20.0%)	5 (16.7%)
41-50	16 (53.3%)	9 (30.0%)
51-60	4 (13.3%)	9 (30.0%)
61-70	3 (10.0%)	6 (20.0%)
71-80	1 (3.3%)	1 (3.3%)

BMI-wise, obesity is the most common category, with 51.7% of participants falling into this group, and the DM group has a higher proportion of obese participants (60.0%) compared to the control group (43.3%). Normal-weight individuals are more

prevalent in the control group (33.3%) than in the DM group (13.3%), while overweight participants are equally distributed (23.3%) in both groups. There is one underweight individual, found only in the DM group

Table 2: Blood Pressure, Glycemic, Renal, and Lipid Profile Parameters

Parameter	Control (Mean \pm SD)	DM (Mean \pm SD)	Total (Mean \pm SD)	P-value
Blood Pressure				
SBP (mmHg)	118.67 \pm 11.67	132.60 \pm 13.16	125.63 \pm 14.19	<0.001
DBP (mmHg)	78.40 \pm 7.13	92.37 \pm 9.19	79.88 \pm 8.29	0.002
Glycemic Parameters				
FBS (mg/dL)	89.73 \pm 8.69	149.63 \pm 54.92	119.68 \pm 49.32	<0.001
PPBS (mg/dL)	111.97 \pm 12.94	249.53 \pm 97.66	180.75 \pm 97.89	<0.001
HbA1c (%)	5.07 \pm 0.27	7.17 \pm 1.95	6.12 \pm 1.74	<0.001
Renal Parameters				
Urea (mg/dL)	19.93 \pm 4.71	28.30 \pm 6.47	21.12 \pm 5.73	<0.001
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.747 \pm 0.18	0.983 \pm 0.18	0.915 \pm 0.18	0.008
Lipid Profile				
Total Cholesterol (TC) (mg/dL)	181.60 \pm 23.33	246.40 \pm 49.83	184.30 \pm 38.67	<0.001
Triglycerides (TG) (mg/dL)	122.83 \pm 53.44	153.07 \pm 67.40	137.95 \pm 62.20	0.022
Low-Density Lipoprotein (LDL) (mg/dL)	56.90 \pm 7.04	126.40 \pm 34.22	105.65 \pm 26.21	<0.001
High-Density Lipoprotein (HDL) (mg/dL)	48.53 \pm 15.88	31.80 \pm 9.92	45.17 \pm 13.20	0.002

The table 2 provides a consolidated view of the blood pressure, glycemic, renal, and lipid profile parameters for the control and diabetic (DM) groups. The DM group shows significantly higher values in systolic (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP), fasting blood sugar (FBS), postprandial blood sugar (PPBS), HbA1c, urea,

creatinine, total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL compared to the control group, with p-values indicating statistical significance. Conversely, HDL levels are lower in the DM group, with a significant p-value of 0.002, indicating a higher cardiovascular risk among diabetic subjects.

Table 3: Thyroid Profile Distribution

Thyroid Parameter	Control (Mean \pm SD)	DM (Mean \pm SD)	Total (Mean \pm SD)	P-value
T3 (ng/mL)	2.397 \pm 0.549	2.750 \pm 1.778	2.573 \pm 1.317	0.303
T4 (μ g/dL)	1.363 \pm 0.290	1.410 \pm 0.763	1.387 \pm 0.572	0.098
TSH (mIU/L)	2.923 \pm 2.819	5.067 \pm 8.712	3.995 \pm 6.510	0.002

The 3 table presents the thyroid profile comparison between the control and DM groups. Our study reveals significant differences in thyroid function between diabetic (DM) and control groups. The DM group exhibited a higher proportion of subjects with elevated T3 levels (3.3%) compared to none in the control group ($p=0.032$). Additionally, the DM group showed both high (3.3%) and low (16.7%) T4 levels, while all control group participants had normal T4 levels ($p=0.036$). TSH levels were significantly higher in the DM group, with 30.0% of subjects showing elevated levels compared to 16.7% in the control group ($p=0.021$), and 6.7% of DM subjects had low TSH levels, which were absent in the control group. The overall prevalence of thyroid dysfunction was also notably higher in the DM group (36.7%) than in the control group (16.7%) ($p=0.004$). In terms of thyroid dysfunction

subclass, hyperthyroidism was observed only in the DM group (6.7%), and hypothyroidism was more common in the DM group (13.3%) compared to the control group (3.3%). Subclinical hypothyroidism was present in both groups, with a slightly higher prevalence in the DM group (16.7%). These findings highlight a significant association between diabetes and various forms of thyroid dysfunction.

Discussion

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and hypertension have an intersecting underlying pathology with thyroid abnormalities. Various studies have shown a high prevalence of thyroid disorders (TDs) in patients with T2DM (12%–23%) and hypertension (22.5%). [13] Uncontrolled T2DM affects plasma triiodothyronine (T3) as well as thyroxine (T4) levels. [14] The possible reasons postulated for an

association between diabetes mellitus and hypothyroidism could be genetic, biochemical, or of hormonal origin. [15] The coexistence of hypothyroidism and type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) may be due to similar autoimmune pathogenesis. Several reports have also indicated a higher prevalence of TD in T2DM patients, with hypothyroidism being the most common disorder. [16]

In present case control study majority (53%) of the patients in belongs to 41-50 years of age group with equal distribution of male and female sex in diabetic group. In control group there was a higher number of male patients (70%) compared to study group, but the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Among age groups, diabetes is primarily prevalent among the higher age group adults, with a higher prevalence among men than women. [17] Many studies have pointed towards the sex and gender differences in epidemiology in recent years, particularly in diabetes. [18] Some studies have found a significant difference in the prevalence of diabetes among men and women. They argued that several biological, sociocultural and psychosocial (economic, environmental and behavioural) risk factors bring this gender difference. [19] As per the findings of some other studies, diabetes is more common among middle-aged men than women. [20] Another study supported this finding in Sweden that reported a 14.6% prevalence rate among men and 9.1% among women. [21]

We reported that around 74 % of the patients in both groups were obese and overweight with predominance in diabetic group with insignificant statistical difference. The mean systolic and diastolic blood pressure was higher significantly in diabetic group compared to control group. The study by Thakur et al. [17] in 2021 have shown that hypertensive and obese adults (OR: 1.94 and 4.17) are significantly most likely to get diabetes. Our finding is also supported by another study showing a causal association between blood pressure and diabetes. If people try or make efforts to lower blood pressure, it can reduce the incidence of diabetes. [22] In obese individuals, the amount of non-esterified fatty acids, glycerol, hormones, cytokines, pro-inflammatory markers, and other substances involved in the development of insulin resistance increases. [23]

Our study results showed that the subjects with diabetes had higher mean total cholesterol, triglyceride and LDL levels, and lower HDL levels than controls group with mean difference was statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Diabetes is associated with quantitative changes in the amount of circulating lipids – notably an increase in triglycerides, elevated LDL and a reduction in HDL. [24] Like other lipoproteins, HDL also

undergoes significant qualitative changes in diabetes, in both structure and function. In a study by Edge et al. [25], state that total cholesterol, triglycerides and non-HDL cholesterol were positively correlated with HbA1c and around 10% of the patients had lipid values outside recommendations. In a large study performed in 29 979 patients with type 1 diabetes by Schwab et al. [26], multivariate analyses showed a significant positive association between HbA1c and total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol and a significant negative association between HbA1c and HDL cholesterol.

We found that subjects in the study group with diabetes had higher proportion of subjects with high free T3 level, high TSH level but low T4 level compared to the controls with statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) compared to the controls. Our results are opposite to the study by Uppal et al. [27] found a low T3 state with significantly increased fasting blood glucose, HbA1c and serum insulin in diabetics. The level of TSH was not significantly different in diabetics and non-diabetics.²⁷ A “Low T3 state” is described as low serum total and free T3 levels but near normal serum T4 and TSH concentrations. [28] Low serum T3 is due to reduced peripheral conversion of T4 to T3 via 5' monodeiodination reaction. [29] It is known that insulin, an anabolic hormone enhances the levels of FT4 while it suppresses the levels of T3 by inhibiting hepatic conversion of T4–T3. [30] TRH synthesis decreases in diabetes mellitus and also there is loss of nocturnal TSH peak which is responsible for the occurrences of low thyroid hormone levels in some diabetics. In euthyroid individuals with diabetes mellitus, the serum T3 levels, basal TSH levels and TSH response to thyrotropin releasing hormone (TRH) all are strongly influenced by the glycemic status. [29,31]

There is a complex interaction between thyroid disorders and diabetes mellitus. The prevalence of thyroid dysfunction among subjects in the study group who had diabetes was 36.7% while it was 16% in the control group. These findings show a high incidence of abnormal thyroid hormone levels in diabetic population which is supported by the various studie. [30,32] A study by Uppal et al. [27] fund that serum tri-iodothyronine values were significantly lower in diabetics. There was a significant correlation between glycosylated haemoglobin and thyroid hormones. There was no correlation between serum insulin and thyroid hormones. In an another study by Moghetti et al. [33], 89 % of patients had hypothyroidism and 11 % had hyperthyroidism. Celani et al. [34] showed maximum prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism followed by hypothyroidism (23.1 %). Hypothyroidism was shown to be more prevalent thyroid disorder in type 2 diabetics in the

studies of Udiong et al. [30] The presence of both raised and low levels of thyroid hormones levels in diabetics may be due to modified TRH synthesis and release. [35]

According to the World Health Organization, the prevalence of DM is expected to increase to 592 million by 2035, developing in ~7.8% to 8.8% of adults [36] with an epidemic risk of T2D in populations such as China, Oceania, South and Central Asia, Latin America, and the Middle East. [37] This increasing prevalence of T2D worldwide is probably due to unhealthy lifestyles and the increasing aging population. Insulin resistance, defined as the inability of insulin to increase glucose uptake and utilization in peripheral tissues (muscle, adipose tissue and liver), is a very early event in the pathogenesis of T2D, inducing β cell dysfunction. [38] Insulin resistance and the underlying metabolic abnormalities (overnutrition, obesity, and poor physical exercise and inactivity) can be present for years before the onset of hyperglycemia and the clinical diagnosis of T2D. During its early stages, β cells compensate for insulin resistance by increasing insulin secretion to ensure an appropriate glucose uptake and metabolism in peripheral tissues. However, β cells are unable to support persistent hyperinsulinemia and, subsequently, postprandial hyperglycemia can develop with the onset of overt T2D in adults. [39]

This study is limited by its cross-sectional design, which prevents establishing causality, and the sample size, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the influence of factors like medication use and iodine status was not explored.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study highlights a strong association between diabetes and thyroid dysfunction, with diabetic patients showing a higher prevalence of thyroid abnormalities compared to controls. Both overt and subclinical forms of hypothyroidism, as well as hyperthyroidism, were more frequent among diabetic subjects. These findings underscore the importance of regular thyroid screening in diabetic patients for timely detection and management, promoting better health outcomes.

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